

Oxomolybdenum(V) Complexes of Some Multidentate N-O Donors

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A number of oxomolybdenum(V) complexes of some multidentate N—O donors in the form of Schiff bases have been synthesised and studied. The Schiff bases were obtained by condensing aromatic acid hydrazides with salicylaldehyde (ligands designated as L_1H_2) and with biacetylmonoxime (ligands designated as L_2H_2). All these ligands exhibit tridentate function in forming the complexes. The ligands L_1H_2 formed complexes of the type $MoO(L_1H)Cl_2$ (Type A), whereas L_2H_2 yielded complexes of the type $Mo_2O_3(L_2H)_2Cl_2$ (Type B). All the type A complexes are mononuclear, while the type B complexes are binuclear with oxygen-bridging between two Mo atoms. The isolated complexes were characterised by elemental analysis, spectroscopic (uv-visible, ir), magnetic and conductance data.

THE use of oximes and Schiff bases as coordinating agents towards transition and non-transition metal ions forms an important and interesting subject in coordination chemistry. Similarly, metal-complexes of aliphatic and aromatic acidhydrazides have also been studied in considerable details¹⁻⁸. But, comparatively less attention has been given to the class of ligands containing both the oxime and the acidhydrazide or the azomethine and the acidhydrazide functions in the same molecule. Although some work on the transition metal complexes of such ligands have recently been published⁹⁻²¹, literature shows that no work has been done on the compounds of such ligands with molybdenum, the complex chemistry of which has of late gathered much importance due to the participation of variable-valence molybdenum cofactors in several redox enzyme systems. A report on some simple oxomolybdenum(V) complexes is presented in this communication.

The ligands used in the present study were of the Schiff base type, obtained through the condensation of salicylaldehyde or biacetylmonoxime with aromatic acidhydrazides in ethanol medium. The acidhydrazides used in the synthesis of the ligands were benzhydrazide, *ortho*-amino-, *para*-amino-, *ortho*-hydroxy-, *ortho*-chloro-, *para*-chloro- and *para*-nitro-benzhydrazides. In the ligands derived from the acidhydrazides and salicylaldehyde (ligands of type I, designated as L_1H_2), the potential donor sites are (i) the carbonyl oxygen, (ii) the azomethine nitrogen and (iii) the phenolic oxygen. In the ligands formed through the condensation of the acidhydrazides with biacetylmonoxime (ligands of type II, designated as L_2H_2), the potential donor sites are (i) the carbonyl oxygen, (ii) the azomethine nitrogen and (iii) the oxime nitrogen. All

of them function as monoprotic tridentate ligands. The ring hydroxyl group of salicylhydrazide in the cases of the respective ligands is not involved in the bond formation with molybdenum, but indeed it has some solubilising effect on the complexes formed.

Except in the case of *ortho*-aminobenzhydrazide (anthranil hydrazide), the above condensation takes place between the hydrazinic NH_2 group of the acidhydrazide and the carbonyl group of salicylaldehyde or biacetylmonoxime. In the case of *ortho*-aminobenzhydrazide, the condensation takes place between the ring NH_2 group instead of the hydrazinic NH_2 group. This has been conclusively proved from the nmr and ir spectra of the free acid hydrazide and its condensation products^{7,12-14}. The donor skeletons of the ligands used in the present study are shown in Fig. 1.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R., B.D.H. grade or of equivalent quality. The ligands were prepared by reacting the acidhydrazides with salicylaldehyde or diacetylmonoxime in 1 : 1 molar proportion in ethanol. On refluxing on water-bath for 3-4 h and subsequent cooling, the compounds separated as crystalline solids. They were filtered by suction and crystallised twice from ethanol. They were analysed for C, H and N, and the results tallied well with the expected theoretical values (Table 1). Ammonium oxopentachloromolybdate was prepared by the standard method¹⁵. The ethanol used throughout the study was lime-distilled, and then refluxed over metallic Mg and a crystal of iodine and redistilled before use.

as the calibrant. Diamagnetic corrections were made using Pascal's constants¹⁶.

Preparation and analyses of complexes: The ligands (0.001 mol) were dissolved by refluxing in dry ethanol and dry N₂ was passed through the solution. Ammonium oxopentachloromolybdate (0.001 mol) was directly added to the solution and the mixture was further refluxed for ~1 h in N₂ atmosphere and then cooled. Solid compounds of type B readily separated out. These were filtered through suction, washed with dry ethanol and dried in vacuum over fused CaCl₂. The complexes of type A remained in solution under these conditions. The cooled solutions were then kept in a vacuum desiccator over solid KOH for 2-3 days, when crystalline compounds separated out. They

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND MAGNETIC MOMENT OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Analysis% : Found/(Calcd.)					μ_{eff} at 30° B.M.
	Mo	N	C	H	Cl	
MoO(BH-SalAld)Cl ₂	22.70 (22.74)	6.60 (6.63)	39.86 (39.81)	2.56 (2.60)	16.85 (16.82)	1.70
MoO(o-ABH-SalAld)Cl ₂	22.05 (21.96)	9.68 (9.61)	38.30 (38.44)	2.76 (2.74)	16.30 (16.24)	1.68
MoO(p-ABH-SalAld)Cl ₂	22.10 (21.96)	9.72 (9.61)	38.26 (38.44)	2.78 (2.74)	16.22 (16.24)	1.65
MoO(o-HBH-SalAld)Cl ₂	22.00 (21.91)	9.30 (9.39)	38.46 (38.35)	2.49 (2.51)	16.16 (16.21)	1.61
MoO(o-CBH-SalAld)Cl ₂	21.12 (21.02)	6.02 (6.13)	36.92 (36.80)	2.15 (2.19)	23.25 (23.32)	1.74
MoO(p-CBH-SalAld)Cl ₂	20.95 (21.02)	6.10 (6.13)	36.85 (36.80)	2.22 (2.19)	23.40 (23.32)	1.54
MoO(p-NBH-SalAld)Cl ₂	20.46 (20.55)	9.08 (8.99)	35.82 (35.97)	2.17 (2.14)	15.32 (15.20)	1.66
Mo ₂ O ₃ (BH-DAMO) ₂ Cl ₂	25.78 (25.70)	11.30 (11.24)	35.16 (35.34)	3.25 (3.21)	9.56 (9.50)	0.52
Mo ₂ O ₃ (o-ABH-DAMO) ₂ Cl ₂	24.85 (24.71)	14.32 (14.41)	33.87 (33.97)	3.37 (3.34)	9.05 (9.13)	0.46
Mo ₂ O ₃ (p-ABH-DAMO) ₂ Cl ₂	24.92 (24.71)	14.36 (14.41)	34.15 (33.97)	3.32 (3.34)	9.22 (9.13)	0.48
Mo ₂ O ₃ (o-HBH-DAMO) ₂ Cl ₂	24.82 (24.64)	10.75 (10.78)	34.06 (33.88)	3.10 (3.08)	9.17 (9.11)	0.22
Mo ₂ O ₃ (o-CBH-DAMO) ₂ Cl ₂	23.40 (23.52)	10.40 (10.29)	32.50 (32.35)	2.74 (2.69)	17.32 (17.40)	0.32
Mo ₂ O ₃ (p-CBH-DAMO) ₂ Cl ₂	23.38 (23.52)	10.36 (10.29)	32.25 (32.35)	2.76 (2.69)	17.28 (17.40)	0.25
Mo ₂ O ₃ (p-NBH-DAMO) ₂ Cl ₂	22.78 (22.93)	13.45 (13.38)	31.72 (31.54)	2.66 (2.62)	8.57 (8.48)	0.38

* (BH-SalAld) = Schiff base of benzoylhydrazine and salicylaldehyde, (BH-DAMO) = Schiff base of benzoylhydrazine and diacetylmonoxime, A = amino, H = hydrox y, C = chloro, N = nitro.

The electronic spectra in methanol solution were recorded in a Hilger UVISPEC spectrophotometer and the mull-spectra were taken in a MOM-201 (Hungarian) spectrophotometer. The ir spectra were recorded in KBr-matrix in a Beckman IR-20-A spectrophotometer. Electrical conductivity of the soluble complexes were measured in purified redistilled methanol with a Philips PR-9500 conductivity bridge, using a dip-type cell. The room temperature magnetic susceptibility of the complexes were

measured in a Gouy balance, using Hg[Co(SCN)₄] were filtered, washed with a small quantity of dry ethanol and dried in vacuum over solid KOH.

The complexes were analysed for their molybdenum, nitrogen and halogen contents by standard methods. The analytical results, along with the magnetic moment values of the complexes are given in Table-1. The visible and the ir spectral data are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—SOME IMPORTANT INFRARED AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BANDS

Compd.*	$\nu_{\text{Mo}-\text{O}}$	$\nu_{\text{Mo}-\text{O}-\text{Mo}}$	$\nu_{\text{Mo}-\text{Cl}}$	Absorption maxima** cm ⁻¹
MoO(BH-SalAld)Cl ₂	960	—	325390	13300 (30) 19300 (2720)
MoO(o-ABH-SalAld)Cl ₂	950	—	340310	13400 (38) 19600 (2300)
MoO(p-ABH-SalAld)Cl ₂	955	—	320300	14100 (24) 21500 (606)
MoO(o-HBH-SalAld)Cl ₂	960	—	330310	13900 (40) 21300 (2450)
MoO(o-CBH-SalAld)Cl ₂	950	—	350310	13700 (38) 22600 (46)
MoO(p-CBH-SalAld)Cl ₂	965	—	330310	13700 (23) 19000 (250)
MoO(p-NBH-SalAld)Cl ₂	970	—	325295	14700 (300) 21700 (950)
Mo ₂ O ₃ (BH-DAMO) ₂ Cl ₂	972	730500	320300	18200 (8200)
Mo ₂ O ₃ (o-ABH-DAMO) ₂ Cl ₂	970	737508	340305	20400 (1435)
Mo ₂ O ₃ (p-ABH-DAMO) ₂ Cl ₂	975	725490	320290	19840 (7550)
Mo ₂ O ₃ (o-HBH-DAMO) ₂ Cl ₂	975	732515	325300	19500 (5200)
Mo ₂ O ₃ (o-CBH-DAMO) ₂ Cl ₂	960	740512	340310	19400 (7000)
Mo ₂ O ₃ (p-CBH-DAMO) ₂ Cl ₂	950	736510	330310	19800 (4500)
Mo ₂ O ₃ (p-NBH-DAMO) ₂ Cl ₂	965	745500	320295	19700 (5020)

* Abbreviation as in Table 1.

** Figures in parentheses indicate ϵ_{max} values.

Results and Discussion

Composition and conductance of complexes: The complexes of the acidhydrazones of salicylaldehyde possess the general formula MoO(L₁H)Cl₂ (type A complexes) and those of acidhydrazones of biacetylmonoxime have the general formula Mo₂O₃(L₂H)₂Cl₂ (type B complexes). They are fairly stable in air. The complexes of type A are soluble in methanol and DMF, but those of type B are insoluble in methanol and soluble in DMF. The extremely low conductance values of the complexes suggest their non-electrolytic nature. Hence, it is concluded that the Cl atoms in these complexes are coordinated to the metal ion.

Magnetic moments of complexes: All the complexes of type A have magnetic moment values (at ~ 30°) lying in the range 1.6-1.7 B.M., which are consistent with the presence of one unpaired electron per metal atom in the complexes. This indicates that these complexes are mononuclear¹⁷. The effective magnetic moment, calculated per atom of molybdenum in the complexes of type B are less than 0.5 B.M., which is less than the spin-only value (1.73 B.M.) for Mo^V. This suggests that the Mo^V complexes of type B are at least binuclear^{18,19} in which the Mo^V centres are bridged by oxygen, permitting some kind of super-exchange which leads to partial quenching of the magnetic moment of the coupled d¹-system.

Ir spectra of complexes: All the complexes of type A exhibit (Table 2) one strong band in the region 945-970 cm⁻¹, which is assigned to the terminal $\nu_{\text{Mo}-\text{O}}$ ²⁰. Such bands, appearing at the lower frequency range, cannot be attributed to the Mo-O-Mo bridge. But, the complexes of type B

exhibit one strong band at 945-980 cm⁻¹ (assigned to the terminal $\nu_{\text{Mo}-\text{O}}$), and a medium band at 430-450 cm⁻¹ region and a weak band at 750-780 cm⁻¹ attributed to the symmetric and anti-symmetric bridge vibrations of the Mo₂O₃⁴⁺ moiety^{21,22}, respectively. The far ir spectra of all the complexes of types A and B exhibit strong, incompletely resolved absorptions in the 250-350 cm⁻¹ region which may be assigned²³ to $\nu_{\text{Mo}-\text{Cl}}$.

In the ir spectra of the complexes of type A (except the one obtained from the condensation product of salicylhydrazide and salicylaldehyde), there is no sharp band in the region 3500-3790 cm⁻¹, which clearly indicates that the phenolic OH group of salicylaldehyde component of the ligands has undergone deprotonation during complexation with the metal ion. The strong band of the ligands at 1660-1640 cm⁻¹, taken to be the amide I band, is always shifted to lower frequency side by 15-40 cm⁻¹ in the complexes. This indicates the participation of the C=O group of the hydrazide component in the coordination. The frequency of vibration of the azomethine group of the ligands in the region 1610-1600 cm⁻¹ is found to be shifted by 5-10 cm⁻¹ in the metal complexes. This may be taken as an evidence of coordination to the metal from the azomethine nitrogen.

The ir spectra of the complexes of type B show shifting of the carbonyl and azomethine frequencies similar to those of type A complexes (as stated above) and thus indicate their participation in coordination to molybdenum. The presence of the $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ of the amide I band (shifted, however, towards lower frequency side by 15-40 cm⁻¹ due to the coordination with the metal ion) in all the complexes of types A and B, clearly suggests that the

hydrazide portion of the ligands remains in tact in the keto-form in all the complexes. Hence, in the complexes of type B, deprotonation must have occurred from the oxime group, establishing a bond between the metal ion and the oxime nitrogen. This is substantiated²⁴ by the increase of $\nu_{C=N}$ (of the oxime group) towards higher side by 25-65 cm^{-1} .

Electronic spectra of complexes: The solution spectra of type A complexes consist of a number of ill-defined absorption bands. A weak band at 13000-14000 cm^{-1} is tentatively assigned to the $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}$, d_{yz} transition in octahedral ligand field. A band of medium intensity at 22000 cm^{-1} region is tentatively assigned to the $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ transition in octahedral symmetry²⁵. The third d-d transition ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$) is covered by the more intense charge transfer band which is observed above 26000 cm^{-1} . In the cases of type B complexes, a strong band at 19000 cm^{-1} is assigned to d-d transition and is indicative of the presence of $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3^{4+}$ species²⁶. The high ϵ_{max} values, particularly in the type B complex, are probably due to the overlap of the d-d transition bands with that of the ligand \rightarrow metal charge transfer band.

From the above considerations, the complexes of type A and type B may be represented by the following structures (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2.

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